

Housing Problem in Turkey and Policy Implementations for Solution

1. BACKGROUND: INTRODUCTION AND IDENTIFICATION OF THE PROBLEM

Although it has been more than 150 years since Frederick Engels' "The Housing Problem" (Frederick Engels, 1872) was written, it is still relevant today. Urban land today is in high demand and is appreciating in value at an incredible rate, but an increasing number of people are finding it difficult to pay the market land prices and housing rents.

One of the major issues we face today is housing issue, especially in the context of the modernization of capitalism and the rise of the private property ideology. The need for housing (shelter) is one of the security needs in Maslow's hierarchy of needs, which come after the physiological needs (such as food and drink), which are the most essential for an individual's survival and are in the second layer. (Maslow, A., & Lewis, K. J., 1987).

There have been speculative increases in the housing market in urban centers, particularly with the spread of mechanized agriculture and the rise in migration from rural to urban areas. A wide range of scientists, from architects to civil and environmental engineers, from economists to other social scientists, are interested in the housing issue in addition to its economic, social, and familial dimensions. In this regard, the topic has evolved into one of the most crucial issues in government policies, even with being one of the most crucial areas of public policy.

Due to growing urbanization and some economic issues, housing, and particularly rent issues, have emerged as a significant issue in Turkey, the European nation with the fastest population growth. Regarding current affairs, price increases in Turkey and everywhere else were a result of the Covid-19 pandemic's detrimental effects on the global economy as well as the ongoing conflict in Ukraine. Additionally, the rise in housing market input costs contributed to an increase in rent. In terms of domestic reasons, the Turkish economy has been experiencing worsening trends for the past five years. Turkey's annual inflation rate has reached 70%, and as of 2021, the Turkish Lira has lost 75% of its value (Al Jazeera, 2022). The rise in rental prices is also influenced by the appearance of opportunists in the real estate markets. As a result, rental prices in Turkey increased by 152% in the last 1 year compared to the previous year, and increased by 233% in the last 4 years. (Mynet, 2022).

Rents are regarded as a significant component of the core value of home prices in academic studies. (Hamilton & Schwab, 1985). Since Turkey's economy changed to an inflation targeting regime in the early 2000s, there have been significant increases in housing prices over the past 15 years as a result of the economic reforms and swift economic growth that were instituted. On the other hand, the real price increases in the housing market sparked discussions about the potential for a Turkish housing bubble (Abioğlu, 2020).

The "sales of residences for foreigners" are another factor influencing the rise in rental rates. Approximately 5 million immigrants and refugees from Syria, Afghanistan, and Ukraine are considered to have been living in Turkey right now. Due to rising demand from both those who have immigrated to Turkey from these nations as a result of the war and those who wish to benefit from being a Turkish citizen by purchasing a home in Turkey from another country, house prices and rent have skyrocketed.

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The majority of Turkish citizens with low incomes are forced to relocate to areas further from the city centers as a result of the high rate of increase in rental prices. Apart from that, the rise in home sales keeps going up. According to the most recent report from the Turkish Statistical Institute (TURKSTAT), which was released in August 2022, the number of houses sold in Turkey between January and August 2022 and totaling 943 thousand 791 increased by 17.7% compared to the same period the previous year (*TÜİK Kurumsal*, 2022). This shows that citizens go to own houses with large debts to avoid high rent prices, and it may also indicate that opportunists who want to benefit from high rental incomes are increasing.

Figure 1: House prices in Turkey
[House price index (2017=100)]

Source: (Global Property, 2022)

2. IDENTIFYING MARKET FAILURE

First of all, it's crucial to stress that markets are ineffective at allocating resources. The housing problem cannot be solved solely by the market economy, like most problems. The rise in housing prices in Turkey and the rest of the world is due to inadequate resource distribution and neoliberal policy's main goal, "maximizing profits." The desire of private construction companies to make highest profit is one of the main reasons for the increase in housing prices.

There are some opportunists in the real estate market and real estate sector, according to Nurettin Nebati, Former Minister of Treasury and Finance of the Republic of Turkey. "They negatively impact the market by creating artificial price increases that upset the equilibrium between supply and demand. We will find out who failed to accurately report their income from home sales and rent price increases." he said. He highlighted the market's shortcomings (milliyet.com, 2022).

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The market economy cannot always provide a Pareto-effective distribution on its own, and it is insufficient to provide economic efficiency in some areas. The problem in housing rents in Turkey is also due to this inadequacy of the market.

One of the important factors causing market failure in the production of social housing is that it is not possible for the private sector to realize the investments that require large expenditures to eliminate the negative externalities in the housing sector under market conditions. Here, the situations where negative externalities are experienced most intensely are the spread of constructions called slums throughout the country, especially in big cities, and a significant increase in the number of homeless people.

Ensuring perfect competition in the housing market and getting rid of "externality" are challenging problems. To address this failure, the state intervenes in the market, but in Turkey this is insufficient.

3. RESPONSIBLE PUBLIC SECTOR TO SOLVE THE PROBLEM

It is impossible to fully express that there is certainty, integrity, stability, and consistency in the public housing policies that have been implemented so far in Turkey in relation to the housing problem. This situation continues to be a significant barrier to the creation of a workable housing problem solution.

Given the state of the market, it might not be possible to fully meet the housing needs of the low- and middle-income groups in society. Under these circumstances, the state must adopt an active policy in the development of social housing. The government, may carry out activities related to the production of social housing directly through the central or local governments, or indirectly by offering financial incentives to housing cooperatives or independent producers.

The public sector in Turkey established the Mass Housing Development Administration ("TOKİ" in Turkish) in 1984 to solve the problems experienced in the housing market. TOKİ, a public institution affiliated to the Ministry of Environment, Urbanization and Climate Change of the Republic of Turkey, established especially for the production of social housing, aims to make low-income people homeowners. TOKİ also states that their houses are earthquake resistant. TOKİ has sold more than 1 million apartments since 1984 and aims to meet 10% of Turkey's housing needs (TOKİ, 2022).

It is important to note that the target income group cannot receive ownership of these homes from the state through social housing production activities. Actually, it is standard procedure to transfer ownership of social housing created and to manage it through rent.

There are some reasons behind the state's direct or indirect activities in the production of social housing. It is thought that the most important of these reasons is the market failures in this regard. Similarly, the state's income distribution policies and the property quality of the house are among these reasons.

In order to solve the problem of exorbitant prices in the sale and rental of housing in Turkey, the Turkish government has intervened in the market by taking several important decisions, especially in the last year. The most important of these is the limitation of rent increases - regardless of inflation - to a maximum of 25 percent. Considering that the annual inflation rate in Turkey has reached 80 percent, the importance of limiting the increase in rent prices to 25 percent can be better

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understood. The second and other important implementation was the announcement of the largest "social housing project" in the country's history, announced by Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdoğan in September this year. According to this project, TOKI will build new affordable housing for low-income families in all cities in Turkey, with applications due from mid-October until the end of November.

3.1 Policy Goals Design

In terms of policy goals, the government made an effort to include policy goals aimed at resolving many of the issues with Turkey's housing market that were previously mentioned. The first of these is the "public housing policy" that the state is presently putting into practice. Housing policy: This includes any direct or indirect interventions in this area, as well as the legislative and operational steps taken within the state's prioritized framework for addressing the social housing crisis. In this context, the term "state" encompasses both local and national governments. Similar to this, the measures taken may apply to the entire nation, a specific area, or they may be tailored to the population below a certain income level. The government ought to get more involved in the housing crisis and defend its people from the free market. It is essential that the national government and local governments cooperate to find a solution. The "public housing policy" should be expanded by state and local governments in two ways:

- (1) Steps to ensure a smooth and integrated partnership between the public and private sectors in the housing market will be prioritized. It is essential for the government to carry out tasks like establishing rules for how the housing market should operate, giving producers and consumers in this sector access to credit, using a mechanism to control supply and demand, and directly building housing for low-income groups in the community.
- (2) In order to counteract harmful externalities in the market, the government should engage in production activities. The quantity of state-built homes should rise as a result of government market intervention. Additionally, it may "physically restrict" the private sector, impose new "taxes" (income tax for businesses with high profits from home sales), or enact new property rights regulations in order to combat the negative externalities brought on by the private sector.

3.2 Policy Instruments

The classification of responsibility for public housing policies between the national government and local governments, as well as the choice of appropriate policy instruments, are all influenced by a variety of factors. The most crucial element will be the priorities that will be decided upon in accordance with that nation's economic, social, and political structure. In actuality, a nation's top priorities should be to satisfy the housing needs of the low-income population living in crowded areas, safeguard the architectural and historical integrity of the cities, or stimulate the overall economy by increasing the volume of housing transactions. In these circumstances, the following three situations require special consideration: (1) Social housing project; (2) Urban transformation strategies; and (3) A general focus on policies relating to the regulation and growth of the housing market and production.

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Subsidies, taxation and incentives policies are the most effective political tool for regulating housing market prices. The government has started to impose additional taxes on private sector companies that make excessive profits in the housing market and sell houses at exorbitant prices. With the new taxation implementation, the price increase in housing prices has been fixed for a considerable period of time and companies that make excessive profits have to pay additional taxes to the state.

The government also increased market intervention with new regulations. In actuality, the government caps the annual increase in rental prices at 25%. Similar regulatory tools are being used to try to solve the housing market crisis.

"Incentives" should be used as another policy tool to address Turkey's housing shortage. The public and private sectors can both receive incentive loans from the government. A ceiling price for housing can be applied with the incentives to be given to lower the private sector's input costs in the construction sector. Additionally, citizens who want to purchase housing should be given access to low-interest loans.

4. REAL POLICY IMPLEMENTATION

In Turkey, there are intense migrations from rural areas or underdeveloped cities to metropolitan cities such as Istanbul, Ankara, Izmir and Bursa. Today, Istanbul is the most populous city in Europe with a population of over 15 million (statista.com, 2020). After all sure, the housing issue cannot be viewed in isolation from economic development. The Turkish government should mobilize development efforts for areas outside of major cities in order to stop the migration to metropolitan cities.

Figure 2: Change of Urban and Rural Population in Turkey

Source: (Yücer, 2020)

New housing shortages and the effects of "illegal housing" are brought about by immigration to major cities. Furthermore, it is clear that families with low incomes, particularly students, struggle to find housing due to high rents.

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The Ministry of Environment and Urbanization, the Ministry of Treasury and Finance, the Undersecretariat of Housing, TOKI, and local governments should collaborate to find a solution to this issue in Turkey. The political conflict between the opposition parties in charge of Istanbul, Ankara, and Izmir's three metropolitan municipalities and the ruling party in charge of Turkey's central government makes it difficult to address the housing crisis.

Since the monopoly of housing production and control by the government in the entire nation is problematic, actively involving municipalities in this matter could be an efficient course of action. For instance, mass housing initiatives have proven successful in Britain and Scandinavian nations. In these nations, it is clear that municipalities have played a significant role in the process by assuming leadership roles in housing cooperatives or joining forces with them, transferring their land to mass housing institutions, offering priority infrastructure services, providing loans, or commit the loans they have already received from other sources (Nevin Peynircioğlu & Belma Üstünişik, 1994).

If we look at the two important implementations already in place, let's first consider the regulation that limits the annual increase in rental prices to 25%. Here, we see that landlords are posing some difficulties. For example, forcing the renter to move out of the house, increasing the rent above the specified rate, etc. In August and September 2022, according to the data of the Turkish Statistical Institute, the rent increase was 49.65% and above (TÜİK, 2022). This is almost double the upper limit of 25%. Here, it shows us that the policy is not actually implemented on the ground. For example, a house with a monthly rent of 10,000 Turkish liras should be worth a maximum of 12,500 Turkish liras in the new rental contract, but in reality, it is 15,000 Turkish liras.

Another question mark concerns the project announced as the largest "social housing project" in the country's history, which aims to make low-income families homeowners. According to official government figures, more than 2 million people applied for the project. The first 250,000 houses to be built under the project will be offered for sale with a 40 percent discount. So what will happen after 250 thousand houses? One of the application requirements was to be between the ages of 18-30. So, is there a plan for those over the age of 30, with low income and who do not own a house? There is also a general discussion about the delivery of the houses on the specified dates. Considering the continuous increase in input costs, the Ukraine crisis and geopolitical difficulties, it seems difficult to deliver the houses within 2 years.

5. CONCLUSION

In Turkey, especially after 1980, the negative consequences of the neoliberal economy, which minimized the effectiveness of the state in the economy and made neoliberal economics dominant in the country and in the market, are also seen in the housing market. The Turkish government should first and foremost expand the tools of state intervention in the market and wage a determined struggle. Moreover, the incompatibility between the central government and local governments does not help to solve the problem. According to government data, house sales fell by more than 20 percent in September and October 2022 (TÜİK, 2022). This shows that the negative impact of the housing market and the problem of overpricing still persists. Of course, the contraction in Turkey's economic situation and the decline in the purchasing power of the Turkish people also play a major role.

Figure 3: Housing sales in Turkey, October 2022

Source: (TUİK, 2022)

Consequently, it is advised that the aforementioned central and local governments, as well as public institutions, take the following actions to address the issue of skyrocketing housing prices:

- Increasing social housing production through TOKİ
- Creating incentives to reduce input costs in housing production
- Taking coercive measures against the private sector, which makes high profits and creates a “bubble” in the market
- Turkey Real Estate Credit Bank should provide low interest loans to producers and consumers
- Giving individual or collective housing loans, making applications for the development of village architecture, transformation of slum areas, preserving and renewing the historical texture and local architecture, and providing interest subsidies on all these loans when necessary by lending projects on these issues.
- Supporting the industry related to residential construction or those working in this field
- Establishing companies related to the housing sector or being a partner in established companies and financial institutions
- Constructing, encouraging and supporting housing and social facilities and infrastructure at the same time, if necessary, in regions where natural disasters occur
- Increasing “urban transformation projects” in order to reduce illegal structures
- Among the shantytowns formed around the cities, the rehabilitation works of the ones that can be adapted to the city are started first and the necessary infrastructure services are completed there, and the liquidation process is started in the areas that cannot be rehabilitated, as well as preventing the construction of new slums.
- Provision of land for mass housing areas
- Ensuring harmony between the government and the opposition should be among the important policy objectives.

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